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**STRESS–STRAIN MODELLING
OF A POROUS SPHERICAL BODY UNDER COMPRESSION**

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Annotation: This paper develops a mathematical model for the stress-strain state of a porous spherical body under uniform compressive loading, taking into account the elastic-viscoplastic behavior of the compressed skeleton. The deformation process is divided into elastic deformation of the porous medium and inelastic deformation of the skeleton. Analytical solutions are obtained within an axisymmetric formulation, and the evolution of the elastic–plastic interface is determined. Numerical results illustrate the influence of material parameters on the stress–strain distribution.

Keywords: porous material, spherical body, stress-strain state, elastic-viscoplasticity, compression

**МОДЕЛИРОВАНИЕ НАПРЯЖЕНИЯ-ДЕФОРМАЦИИ
ПОРИСТОГО СФЕРИЧЕСКОГО ТЕЛА ПРИ СЖАТИИ**

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Аннотация: В данной работе разработана математическая модель напряженно-деформационного состояния пористого сферического тела при равномерной сжимающей нагрузке,

учитывающая упруго-вязкопластическое поведение сжатого каркаса. Процесс деформации разделен на упругую деформацию пористой среды и неупругую деформацию каркаса. Аналитические решения получены в рамках осесимметричной постановки задачи, и определена эволюция упруго-пластической границы раздела. Численные результаты иллюстрируют влияние параметров материала на распределение напряжения и деформации.

Ключевые слова: пористый материал, сферическое тело, напряженно-деформационное состояние, упруго-вязкопластичность, сжатие

Introduction

The analysis of stress–strain states in porous materials is an important problem in continuum mechanics due to its wide applications in geomechanics, material science, and engineering structures. Porous media exhibit complex mechanical behaviour because their deformation involves both the response of the pore space and the solid skeleton. In particular, under compressive loading, the collapse of pores and the subsequent deformation of the compressed skeleton significantly affect the overall mechanical response of the material.

Mathematical modelling of such processes has been extensively studied. In [1], general approaches to modelling granular and porous media were developed, providing a theoretical basis for describing their deformation behaviour. The application of perturbation methods to stability problems in deformable media was considered in [2], while the stability of elastic–viscoplastic deformation processes was investigated in [3]. A related study on porous cylindrical and spherical bodies under compression, taking into account the inelastic behaviour of the skeleton, was presented in [4-8].

Despite these contributions, the coupled analysis of elastic deformation of the porous medium and viscoplastic deformation of the compressed skeleton in spherical geometry remains insufficiently studied. Therefore, this paper aims to develop a mathematical model describing the stress–strain state of a porous spherical body under uniform compression, considering the hardening elastic–viscoplastic properties of the compressed

skeleton. Analytical solutions are obtained, and the evolution of the elastic–plastic interface is analysed.

Main Results

A mathematical model is constructed to describe the stress–strain state of a spherical body for materials with a porous structure, whose compressed skeleton possesses hardening elastic–plastic properties. The deformation of the porous medium under uniformly distributed compressive loads is divided into two interrelated stages: elastic deformation of the porous medium and inelastic deformation of the compressed matrix.

The construction of the mathematical model describing the stress–strain state of the spherical body is carried out within an axisymmetric formulation. Analytical solutions are obtained. As compatibility conditions, the continuity of stress and displacement components at the elastic–plastic interface is imposed, as well as the condition of zero plastic strains at this boundary.

The deformation of a porous material with an initial porosity ε_0 is divided into two interrelated stages [1]. The first stage corresponds to elastic deformation of the compressible porous medium, and the second stage corresponds to inelastic deformation of the compressed skeleton with hardening viscous elastic–plastic properties. The relationship between stresses and strains at the first stage is taken in the form of Hooke’s law for a compressible body, while at the second stage, the elastic deformations of the compressed skeleton obey Hooke’s law for an incompressible body [2]. In the plastic deformation zone of the compressed skeleton, a model of an incompressible hardening elastic-viscoplastic body is used [3].

The total strain in the plastic zone is represented as the sum of elastic and plastic components:

$$\varepsilon_j^\beta = \varepsilon_j^e + \varepsilon_j^p, \quad (1)$$

while the volumetric components of plastic and elastic strains satisfy the incompressibility conditions:

$$\varepsilon_{nn}^p = 0, \varepsilon_{nn}^e = -\varepsilon_0. \quad (2)$$

Let b and a denote the outer and inner radii of the spherical body, respectively. Uniformly distributed compressive loads of intensity q_b act on the outer surface, and q_a on the inner surface.

The rheological relations, plasticity condition, expressions (1), (2), together with the equilibrium equations, Cauchy relations, boundary conditions, and interface conditions, form a closed mathematical model describing the stress–strain state of the spherical body during both stages: elastic deformation of the porous medium and inelastic deformation of the compressed skeleton.

The attainment of zero initial porosity during elastic deformation occurs simultaneously throughout the body under loading conditions described in [4].

The stress–strain state at the first stage of deformation (i.e., in the presence of uncollapsed pores), as well as at the moment of pore collapse (when the initial porosity reaches zero), is determined by relations given in [4-8].

If the porosity condition is not satisfied, a plastic zone arises near the inner surface and expands. In this case, the compressed skeleton deforms as a hardening viscous incompressible elastic–plastic medium with parameters

$$\mu = 1 + \mu_0, k, c, \eta.$$

All relations are further written in dimensionless form. Quantities with dimensions of stress are normalized by μ_1 , and those with dimensions of length by the radius b . The radial component of displacement is denoted by u .

The stress-strain state of the compressed skeleton of the spherical body is determined as follows:

In the elastic region ($\gamma < r < 1$)

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_r &= \frac{1}{3} \left(1 - \frac{1}{r^3}\right) \left(\frac{8\chi\eta k\sqrt{3}}{c+2\mu} \left(3\gamma^2 \dot{\gamma} \left(e^{-\frac{c+2\mu}{\eta}t} - 1 \right) - \frac{c+2\mu}{\eta} \gamma^3 \right) + \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \frac{(3qaf(\varepsilon_0) - \varepsilon_0(3\lambda_1+2))\mu_0 a^3}{3} \right) - q_b, \\ \sigma_\theta &= \frac{1}{3} \left(2 + \frac{1}{r^3}\right) \left(\frac{4\chi\eta k\sqrt{3}}{c+2\mu} \left(3\gamma^2 \dot{\gamma} \left(e^{-\frac{c+2\mu}{\eta}t} - 1 \right) - \frac{c+2\mu}{\eta} \gamma^3 \right) + \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \frac{(3qaf(\varepsilon_0) - \varepsilon_0(3\lambda_1+2))\mu_0 a^3}{6} \right) - q_b \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

In the plastic region ($a < r < \gamma$)

$$\varepsilon_r^p = \frac{2}{\sqrt{3}} \frac{\chi k}{(c+2\mu)} \cdot \left(\frac{\gamma^3}{r^3} - 1 \right) \left(1 - e^{-\frac{c+2\mu}{\eta}t} \right), \quad (4)$$

$$\sigma_r = -q_a + \frac{2\chi k}{\sqrt{3}(c+2\mu)} \left(\left(1 - e^{-\frac{c+2\mu}{\eta}t} \right) \left(\frac{r^3}{a^3} - 1 \right) \left(2\mu - \frac{3\eta\gamma^2\dot{\gamma}}{r^3} \right) + 6\mu \ln \frac{a}{r} \right) - (c + 2\mu)\gamma^3 \left(\frac{1}{a^3} - \frac{1}{r^3} \right),$$

$$\sigma_\theta = -q_a + \frac{\chi k}{\sqrt{3}(c + 2\mu)} \left(\left(1 - e^{-\frac{c+2\mu}{\eta}t} \right) \left(6\mu \left(\frac{\gamma^3}{r^3} + \frac{2r^3}{3a^3} - \frac{5}{3} + 2\ln \frac{a}{r} \right) - 3\eta\gamma^2\dot{\gamma} \left(\frac{1}{r^3} + \frac{2}{a^3} \right) \right) - (c + 2\mu)\gamma^3 \left(\frac{1}{r^3} + \frac{2}{a^3} \right) \right). \tag{5}$$

Displacements and total strains

$$u = \frac{D}{r^2} - \frac{\varepsilon_0}{3}r, \varepsilon_r = -\frac{2D}{r^3} - \frac{\varepsilon_0}{3}, \varepsilon_\theta = \varepsilon_\phi = \frac{2D}{r^3} - \frac{\varepsilon_0}{3}.$$

Auxiliary expressions

$$D(t) = \frac{\chi\eta k}{2\sqrt{3}\mu(c + 2\mu)} \left(3\gamma^2\dot{\gamma} \left(e^{-\frac{c+2\mu}{\eta}t} - 1 \right) - \frac{c + 2\mu}{\eta}\gamma^3 \right) + \frac{(3q_a f(\varepsilon_0) - \varepsilon_0(3\lambda_1 + 2\mu_1))\mu_0 a^3}{12\mu\mu_1}. \tag{6}$$

The radius γ separating elastic and plastic regions is determined from:

$$q_b - q_a + \frac{2\chi k\sqrt{3}}{\sqrt{3}(c + 2\mu)} \left[\mu \left(1 - e^{-\frac{c+2\mu}{\eta}t} \right) \left(2 \left(\frac{\gamma^3}{a^3} - 1 \right) + 6\ln \frac{a}{\gamma} \right) + \gamma^2 \left(3m\dot{\gamma} \left(e^{-\frac{c+2\mu}{\eta}t} - 1 \right) - (c + 2\mu)\gamma \right) \left(\frac{1}{a^3} + \frac{1}{3\gamma^3} - \frac{4}{3} \right) + \frac{(3q_a f(\varepsilon_0) - \varepsilon_0(3\lambda_1 + 2))\mu_0}{9} \left(\frac{a^3}{\gamma^3} - a^3 \right) \right] = 0. \tag{7}$$

Numerical results are presented in Figure 1. Curve 1 corresponds to $k = 0.00002$, curve 2 to $k = 0.00005$, and curve 3 to $k = 0.00006$. Other dimensionless parameters are taken as follows: $a = 0.25, b = 1, q_a = 10^{-4}, q_b = 5 \cdot 10^{-4}, c = 10^{-5}, \lambda_1 = 2, \mu_1 = 1, \eta = 0.00032, k = 4 \cdot 10^{-4}, \varepsilon_0 = 0.0016, \mu = 2$.

Figure 1 – Numerical results

Conclusion

A mathematical model describing the stress–strain state of a porous spherical body under uniform compressive loading has been developed. The deformation process is represented as a combination of elastic deformation of the porous medium and viscoplastic deformation of the compressed skeleton. Analytical solutions for both elastic and plastic regions have been obtained within an axisymmetric formulation. The conditions of continuity at the elastic–plastic interface and the evolution of this boundary have been established. The results demonstrate the significant influence of material parameters on the stress distribution and the development of the plastic zone. The proposed model can be used for

further analysis of porous materials under compression and may serve as a basis for more complex numerical and applied studies.

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